

VERBS AND THEIR GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES

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ANNOTATION

Finite verbs in contrastive languages have six common morphological types, realized partly by using (simple) synthetic means (through inflections) and partly through morphisms different analytical modes (compound words, consisting of at least two verb elements). Thus, the categories of person and number are realized synthetically in two contrasting languages, while categories are realized both synthetically and analytically. Verbs present a system of finite and non-finite forms.

Non-finite (or verbal) forms are four in number, which are: infinitives, gerunds, present participles, past participles. Verbs in finite form have the morphological categories of person, number, tense, aspect, voice and mood.

Keywords: category of person, category of voice, category mood, syntactic, morphisms, analytical, contrasting languages, morphological.

Category of person

The category of person represents the relationship between the action and its author with the speaker, indicating that the action is performed by the speaker (first person), the person called by the speaker, the recipient (second person) or someone/something else than the speaker or addressee (3rd person). The number type indicates whether the action was performed by one or more people or by a non-person (to be: am/is/are; was/we). There are three people and two numbers in the finite verb. Tenses in English express the relationship between action time and speech time. Time and duration are not the same. "Time" (including past, present and future) is a concept; tense is a grammatical device.

Category of voice

The distinction between active and passive is often called the voice distinction. It provides different ways to focus attention on different parts of the information. When talking about people or things performing an action, you use the active voice.

E. x. Mr. Smith locks the gate at 6pm every evening.

The storm destroyed dozens of trees.

Thus, the active voice represents the person or thing designated by the subject in the sentence as the agent (author of the action) expressed by the predicate verb. When you want to focus on the person or thing affected by an action, rather than the person or thing performing the action, you use the passive voice.

E. x. The gate is locked at 6pm every evening.

The passive voice is used to indicate that the person or thing designated by the subject of the sentence is not the agent expressed by the predicate verb but is the object of this action. The subject of a passive verb does not act but is affected, it undergoes an action To form the passive voice, all tenses use the corresponding active tense BE + past participle.

E. x. The chair broke during the scuffle.

Category of mood

The distinction (contrast) between imperatives (for facts), imperatives (for requests, instructions) and subjunctives (for unrealities, suppositions and suppositions) is often called mood discrimination. Imperatives are like the base form of verbs. You use imperatives to request or tell someone to do something, or to give advice, warnings, or instructions on how to do something.

E. x. Don't go so fast.

There are very few subjunctive forms in modern English, which often find other ways to indicate that the events being discussed are uncertain or hypothetical. There are two types of subjunctive: Basic verbs for all verbs and persons used to express desires.

E. x. God save the Queen!

SUMMARY COMPLETION: In this article, I can say that grammatical categories determine the relationship between words and phrases to certain parts of speech, based on their position in the syntactic tree. Normal relationships include subject, object and indirect object.

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